

Synthesis and spectral characterization of mixed ligand zinc(II) complexes with heteroaromatic thiosemicarbazones and pyridine/picoline

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Mixed ligand complexes of zinc(II) with thiocarbamic acid [(thiophene-2-yl)methylene]hydrazide (TTMH) and thiocarbamic acid [(thiophene-2-yl)ethylidene]hydrazide (TTEH) as primary ligands and pyridine (py) and 4-picoline (pic) as secondary ligands have been prepared. The primary ligands act as bidentate ligands in all the zinc complexes. The parent compounds, [Zn(TTMH)Cl₂] and [Zn(TTEH)Cl₂] are found to be four-coordinate zinc complexes. Octahedral geometry is assigned for the mixed ligand zinc(II) complexes with TTMH/TTEH and pyridine/picoline.

Zinc plays an important role in the enzyme systems of animals and plants. Zinc(II) acts predominantly as Lewis acid and is found in many enzymes¹. It is of interest to investigate coordination compounds of sulfur containing ligands as certain enzymes and proteins contain sulfur in coordination core (e.g. ZnN₂S, ZnS₃, ZnS₄ etc.).

Although metal complexes of 2-formylthiophene thiosemicarbazone² and 2-acetylthiophene thiosemicarbazone³ have been prepared, there are no reports available in literature on spectral studies of their mixed ligand complexes with thiocarbamic acid [(thiophene-2-yl)methylene]hydrazide (1, TTMH) and thiocarbamic acid [(thiophene-2-yl)ethylidene]hydrazide (2, TTEH) and pyridine or 4-picoline. We therefore decided to synthesize and characterize zinc(II) complexes of TTMH and TTEH and their adducts with pyridine (py) and 4-picoline (4-pic).

R = H : TTMH, 1
R = CH₃ : TTEH, 2

Results and Discussion

All the zinc complexes including the adducts are soluble in DMF. Their molar conductance values are in the range 6.9–8.5 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, which suggest nonelectrolytic nature⁴.

The ligands (TTMH, TTEH) exhibit broad IR bands at

3411, 3407 and 3224, 3242 cm⁻¹ due to asymmetric and symmetric modes of terminal NH₂, respectively. Secondary ν_{NH} bands are observed at 3144 and 3140 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of TTMH and TTEH, respectively, suggesting that these ligands exist in keto form in solid state. These bands are not affected in the spectra of the zinc complexes, indicating the non-participation of amino and hydrazino nitrogen atoms in chelation. This observation also suggests that the ligands coordinate the metal ion in thione form.

Strong bands observed in the IR spectra of TTMH and TTEH at 1596 and 1604 cm⁻¹, respectively, are assigned to ν_{C=N} stretching vibration. In the spectra of the zinc complexes, this band shifted to lower wave numbers (Δν = ~15 cm⁻¹), suggesting the coordination of azomethine nitrogen to zinc.

TTMH and TTEH respectively show strong bands at 1100 and 1092 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ν_{C=S}, and the absence of ν_{S-H} band (2570 cm⁻¹) suggests that the ligands remain in thione form at least in solid state. The downward shift of ν_{C=S} band in the spectra of the zinc complexes suggests the coordination of zinc through sulfur atoms of C=S group. The ν_{C-S} (thiophene ring) vibrations of TTMH and TTEH are observed at 690 and 715 cm⁻¹, respectively. In the spectra of all the zinc complexes, the C-S vibration is not affected, suggesting non-participation of ring sulfur on coordination.

IR spectral data of the adducts are very similar to the zinc complexes. The appearance of new bands which are not observed in the spectra of the parent complexes at 1590–1608 cm⁻¹ region, suggests the coordination of pyridine/picoline nitrogen atoms in mixed ligand complexes.

The pyridine adduct $[Zn(TTEH)Cl_2Py_2]$ shows high field 1H NMR signal at δ 2.331 (s) corresponding to the imino methyl protons. Whereas picoline adduct $[Zn(TTEH)Cl_2Pic_2]$ exhibits singlet at δ 2.332 and 2.339 corresponding to iminomethyl and picoline methyl protons, respectively. Multiplets centred at δ 7.784–7.070, 8.594–7.391 and 8.461–7.273 are assigned to thiophene, pyridine and picoline ring protons, respectively. In all the adducts, the signals appearing at δ 10.283–10.354 and 8.309–8.279 are respectively assigned to NH and NH_2 protons of thiosemicarbazone ligand. The spectral data reveal the formation of 1 : 2 $\{[Zn(L)Cl_2] : B\}$ adducts (where, L = TTMH, TTEH; B = pyridine or picoline).

Based on the above results, the structure of parent zinc complexes (3 and 4) and their adducts (5–8) are respectively assigned to possess tetracoordinate zinc and hexacoordinate zinc containing bases in axial positions.

Experimental

Thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde and methyl-2-thienylketone were of reagent grade (Fluka). Thiosemicarbazide (Loba, G.R.) was crystallized from hot water before use. Solvents were redistilled. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade and used as such. Preparation and characterization of TTMH, TTEH and their copper(II) complexes were reported earlier⁵.

Preparation of zinc complexes :

$[Zn(TTMH)Cl_2]$: A mixture of TTMH (0.0162 mol in 100 ml hot methanol) and zinc chloride (0.0162 mol in 10 ml methanol) was refluxed for 5 h. It was then cooled, evaporated at room temperature and the resulting solid was washed with hot water, cold methanol and dried under reduced pressure, m.p. 205–207°d (Found : C, 22.42; H, 2.09; N, 13.01; Cl, 22.50. Calcd. for : C, 22.40; H, 2.17; N, 13.07; Cl, 23.22%); ν_{max} 3448 (NH_2), 3176 (NH), 1048 (C=S), 690 (C–S, thiophene), 388 (M–N), 330 cm^{-1} (M–S).

$[Zn(TTEH)Cl_2]$: It was prepared by refluxing a mixture of TTEH (0.010 mol dissolved in 100 ml methanol) and zinc chloride (0.010 mol, dissolved in 10 ml methanol) for

3 h. The resulting solid was washed with hot water, cold methanol and dried under reduced pressure, 270–273°d (Found : C, 25.02; H, 2.69; N, 12.53; Cl, 20.50. Calcd. for : C, 25.05; H, 2.68; N, 12.52; Cl, 22.20%); ν_{max} 3408, 3296 (NH_2), 3174 (NH), 1584 (C=N), 1040 (C=S), 715 (C–S, thiophene), 388 (M–N), 330 cm^{-1} (M–S).

Preparation of adducts with pyridine and picoline :

Zinc complex of TTMH or TTEH (2 g) was placed in a Schlenk tube and dissolved in the base (pyridine or 4-picoline; 3 ml). The solution was stirred magnetically for 30 min and *n*-hexane added. After standing for 3–4 days, the resulting light yellow coloured crystalline solid was washed with hot water and *n*-hexane and dried under reduced pressure over $CaCl_2$.

$[Zn(TTMH)Cl_2Py_2]$: M.p. 135–138° (Found : C, 39.92; H, 3.59; N, 14.39; Cl, 16.15. Calcd. for : C, 40.04; H, 3.54; N, 14.59; Cl, 15.30%); ν_{max} 3422, 3230 (NH_2), 3136 (NH), 1616 (C=N), 1600 (C=N pyridine), 1032 (C=S), 685 (C–S thiophene), 358 (M–N), 349 (M–S), 223 cm^{-1} (M–N pyridine); δ 10.283 (1H, s, imine H), 8.587 (2H, d, pyridine H, 2,6), 8.279 (2H, s, amino H), 7.850 (1H, m, pyridine H 4), 7.771 (1H, m, thiophene H 5), 7.445 (2H, m, pyridine H 3,5), 7.107 (1H, dd, thiophene H 3), 6.595 (1H, q, thiophene H 4).

$[Zn(TTMH)Cl_2Pic_2]$: M.p. 127–130° (Found : C, 42.85; H, 4.40; N, 13.82; Cl, 15.10. Calcd. for : C, 42.56; H, 4.33; N, 13.77; Cl, 14.43%); ν_{max} 3411, 3230 (NH_2), 3144 (NH), 1625 (C=N), 1608 (C=N picoline), 1033 (C=S), 690 (C–S thiophene), 362 (M–N), 330 (M–S), 231 cm^{-1} (M–N picoline ring); δ 10.286 (1H, s, imino H), 8.439 (2H, d, picoline H 2,6), 8.286 (2H, s, amino H), 7.764 (1H, m, thiophene H 5), 7.324 (2H, d, picoline H 3,5), 7.108 (1H, d, thiophene H 3), 6.595 (1H, q, thiophene H 4), 2.353 (3H, s, picoline CH_3).

$[Zn(TTEH)Cl_2Py_2]$: M.p. 145–147° (Found : C, 41.19; H, 3.80; N, 14.03; Cl, 15.50. Calcd. for : C, 41.33; H, 3.85; N, 14.18; Cl, 14.85%); ν_{max} 3404, 3296 (NH_2), 3223 (NH), 1612 (C=N), 1598 (C=N pyridine), 1038 (C=S), 710 (C–S thiophene), 384 (M–N), 322 (M–S), 225 cm^{-1} (M–N pyridine); δ 10.354 (1H, s, imino H), 8.584 (2H, d, pyridine H 2,6), 8.306 (2H, s, amino H), 7.818 (1H, m, pyridine H 4), 7.583 (1H, dd, thiophene H 3), 7.413 (2H, m, pyridine 3,5), 7.085 (1H, q, thiophene H 4), 2.331 (3H, s, acetyl thiophene CH_3).

$[Zn(TTEH)Cl_2Pic_2]$: M.p. 115–117° (Found : C, 43.67; H, 4.33; N, 13.45; Cl, 13.45. Calcd. for : C, 43.72; H, 4.41; N, 13.42; Cl, 14.03%); ν_{max} 3440, 3216 (NH_2), 3136 (NH), 1600 (C=N), 1596 (C=N picoline), 1032 (C=S), 710 (C–S, thiophene), 389 (M–N), 336 (M–S), 227 cm^{-1} (M–N picoline); δ 10.335 (1H, s, imino H), 8.441 (2H, d, picoline H, 2,6), 8.309 (2H, s, amino H), 7.591 (1H, dd, thiophene H, 5), 7.527 (2H, d, picoline H 3,5), 7.085 (1H, q, thiophene

H 4), 2.339 (3H, s, picoline CH₃), 2.332 (3H, s, acetylthiophene CH₃).

Elemental analyses were performed at the R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow, India. Molar conductance, IR, NMR data were obtained as described elsewhere⁶.

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